

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
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EBT Author Responses to Evaluation Comments [TEBT-2025- 0009]

Using Template Version: 21 Oct 2024

Thank you for the time and effort taken to review and provide feedback to our expert commentary. All feedback given thus far has been greatly appreciated. Based on the feedback provided for this round of edits, we thoroughly reviewed our manuscript to strengthen our voice and shift our paper to a strong comment piece. To do this we rearranged and reworked each section of our manuscript to read more frontloaded, so the readers have a clear idea of what our opinions are before diving into the evidence to back up our claims. We worked to apply all comments throughout our manuscript to bring it up to a publishable level. Our response to reviewers now includes section numbers and line numbers to aid the editors as they review our work. Lastly, we have provided in-depth responses to each of the provided comments. We thank you again for the detailed suggestions and helpful guidance through this process. We believe the revised manuscript reflects this.

Comment-by-comment responses

Ref.	Evaluation Comment	Response
1	My understanding of this topic (which is schematic, as I am definitely not a topic expert here) is that the coho salmon research is what alerted people to the problems with PPDs and the limitations of the toxicology research at the	We clarified the context of the paper by tightening up the introduction and rewording the “furthermore” section about salmon. Specifically editing lines 88-95: “Coho salmon seem to be more sensitive to PPDs unlike other freshwater

	<p>time in predicting this. Thus, the paper is not so much "furthermore" about the salmon, as much as it is about summarising what people have been researching since the seminal Science paper, what they have discovered (i.e. recent changes in understanding), and what this implies for future research? I think this is partly what the reviewers were looking for in terms of communicating the unique value of this shorter paper as opposed to a full systematic review. This could be made clearer by revising the context and objectives of the review (the first section of the paper), through some rephrasing and change in emphasis in the introduction. I note that Figure 1 is a nice chronology of the evolution of issues around PPDs, but this chronology for some reason is not really reflected in the text.</p>	<p>species. The coho salmon mortality discovery has opened the door to a new field in ecotoxicology research (Figure 2). More publications starting in 2021 have revealed species, like zebrafish, with assumed higher tolerances to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.(7–18) Additionally, other species and <i>in vitro</i> models like <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> (<i>C. elegans</i>), when exposed to PPDs, have exhibited metabolic changes and dysregulated genes.4,10,19–23 Studies investigating PPD exposure in humans, starting in 2024, reported potential health impacts to those living in areas with high rubber recycling.(19,20,24–26)”</p> <p>We also amended the missing Figure 1 reference, which is now figure 2 (line 90).</p> <p>As for the objective of our manuscript we emphasized how our commentary differs from other commentaries and reviews in lines 107-110: “Other PPD reviews and commentaries have been published covering environmental impacts on individual species. However, our commentary aims to summarize what has been published thus far about the toxic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in multiple aquatic organisms, model organisms, and human cell lines since their discovery in coho salmon.”</p>
2	<p>Please use section numbers and line numbers to help reviewers and editors comment on specific places in the text.</p>	<p>We renumbered the different sections within our paper and added line numbers.</p>
3	<p>When restructuring, I suggest numbering your sections, then numbering the sub-sections, so the structure of the manuscript helps guide the reader through the structure of your argument. As an example of how this might be done (though I am only suggesting for purpose of illustration, as the authors you have the expertise to decide the section structure and headings, not me) I could suggest the following (also note how I suggest keeping the headings short, rather than presenting them as questions - headings generally only need to state the concept of the paragraphs that follow, as this is not a Q&A or FAQ piece).</p> <p>❖ 1 Introduction</p>	<p>We renamed each section to be more concise and removed the questions. Lines 62, 127, 138, 139, 156, 164, 174,182, 194, 195, 220, 244, 282, 283, 303, 320, 321, 344, 362, 383, 395, 401, 407, 415, 423, 439 reflect the amended section and subsection titles.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 2 Methods ❖ 3 Effects on coho salmon ❖ 4 Effects on purportedly tolerant fish species <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 4.1 Zebrafish mortality ❖ 4.2 Zebrafish morphology ❖ 4.3 etc. ❖ 5 Terrestrial organisms ❖ 6 Mechanistic research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ 6.1 Gene regulation ❖ 6.2 Metabolic fate ❖ 6.3 etc 	
4	<p>Since this is a commentary, questions such as “Aquatic Organisms: To what extent are coho salmon (<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>) affected by 6PPD-Q?” cannot strictly be answered - the authors can only give their expert overview of how evidence of harm of 6PPD-Q has evolved in the recent literature. To put it another way: the authors can give their view of the current state of knowledge (they can say what they think is known), but their methods do not allow conclusive statements about the effect of 6PPD-Q on e.g. coho salmon (they should not confuse what they think is known with what is actually known). The latter would need a systematic review methodology, for example. I therefore urge the authors to be very careful throughout that their commenting on the perceived state of knowledge does not slide into factual claims about causal relationships.</p>	<p>Taking this comment into account we thoroughly went through the paper line by line and ensured we did not indicate any causal relationships between the PPDs and the reported effects. We specifically addressed this in section 3, coho salmon. We also did our best to enhance our voice throughout the paper so readers have a better sense of our view of the current state of knowledge.</p>
5	<p>The sentence “For example, in mice, the half-life of 6PPD-Q in blood, urine, and feces were identified to be 5.32, 6.20, and 3.87 hours respectively” is a good example of where the claim is too strong given the source - if it is one study, and half-life is only beginning to be studied, then a phrase like “has been estimated to be” would be more appropriate.</p>	<p>We agree that some of our claims slipped into validation of the author's claims. We have worked to amend all instances of this. We also rewrote the specific sentence in the mouse paragraph to better reflect what the study presented. Lines 294 and 295 reflect this change: “For example, the half-life of 6PPD-Q was studied in mice blood,</p>

	<p>In general, in this paper you should only talk about what other researchers have estimated or measured or concluded, you should not validate or otherwise present their estimates as true.</p>	<p>urine, and feces (5.32, 6.20, and 3.87 hours respectively).”</p>
6	<p>Section “How do PPDs affect zebrafish morphology, behavior, and physiology?” This claim is too strong for a commentary, and even a systematic review would be unlikely to be able to conclude absolute causality in this way. Phrasing such as "There is evidence that both PPDs may cause..." would be more appropriate. Per my comments on front-loading, I could suggest starting out by saying something like "There is recent evidence that 6PPD and 6PPD-Q may have morphological effects, behavioural, and physiological effects in zebrafish, a species originally thought to be tolerant of exposure to PPDs." Then, a paragraph briefly describing the recent studies, one for each issue, with some indication of volume of evidence (I am guessing the number of studies is small? You say elsewhere that the issue is starting to be studied - so it would be a matter of indications rather than causal conclusions?). I would suggest considering this for all sections of the manuscript.</p>	<p>We have changed the section headings for zebrafish (see comment 3). We also reworded our introduction to read more along the lines of what you suggested. Lines 161-163: “As new studies are published, the effects of PPDs seem to extend beyond mortality and into morphological, behavioral, and physiological changes.”</p> <p>We also split the zebrafish section into subsections for morphology, behavior, and physiology, sections 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5.</p> <p>As for the frontloading of each section we did our best to implement this structure throughout the manuscript. Please see comment 8.</p>
7	<p>Section 2. Humans: This is a good example of where there can be more precision in claims made in the paper. The section appears to describe exposure studies, but some of the claims the authors make about the evidence appear to imply that health effects have been studied - and even so, as the authors say these are studies not only of PPD exposures but other pollutants as well. This is why we are cautious about expert commentaries at EBT - it is very easy for authors to veer away from stating facts and making expert observations about emerging evidence, to making claims that reflect their opinion but are not grounded in the studies they have reviewed. The authors must make sure (a) that they differentiate opinions from fact, (b) they distinguish facts about PPDs from facts about the emerging evidence around PPDs, and (c) that claims, be they opinions or facts,</p>	<p>We have reworked the human section (lines 220-243) to carefully differentiate opinion from facts. For opinions, we have changed verbiage to clearly demonstrate author bias (a). We have also ensured facts about PPDs can be distinguished from facts about emerging evidence as the latter has been reworked to clearly appear as opinion (b). Finally, we have thoroughly reviewed the studies to ensure that all statements, factual or opinion, are concretely grounded in science (c).</p>

	are actually strictly correct and grounded in the literature they have been reviewing, especially when b is at stake.	
8	<p>General comment: There is a tendency in the manuscript to what we at EBT call "backloading" an argument. This refers to the process of presenting reasons for a claim or for listing evidence before presenting the claim itself. In a comment article (or most other article types) this requires the reader to read a lot of text without knowing why they are reading it. Once they finally get to the end of the section, they are told why the statements in the section mattered. Then, they have to recall or re-read the section to see if they agree that the argument supports the claim. It is much better for the reader if the argument is frontloaded: state the claim or conclusion first, so the reader knows the claim being made, then explain the reasons for the claim. State what you think first, and why you think it second. (Telling somebody why you think something, without first explaining what you think, would not work very well in conversation.)</p>	<p>Upon rereading our manuscript we completely agree. All sections within the manuscript have been rearranged to read more "front loaded." We implemented a specific structure to each section:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Introduce the topic (b) Point out the gap in research (c) Explain why this is a gap with evidence (d) Wrap up entire paragraph with concluding statement <p>We think this structure of each section works much better and reads smoothly compared to our previous manuscript.</p>
9	<p>Section: "How does the mortality rate in zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>) compare to coho salmon?". Maybe make it clearer in the introduction that (if I understand correctly) the research and regulatory community was first alerted to the specific (and novel / unique?) toxicity of 6PPD-Q in particular when it was discovered that (a) 6PPD is not the toxicant, it is the environmental breakdown product 6PPD-Q, and (b), coho salmon are uniquely vulnerable at a life stage nobody was looking at previously. Then, this section can be very clear about what you as authors think has been learned about coho salmon since that study was published.</p>	<p>For our introduction we focused on clarifying point (b), (lines 157-163) "Since the discovery of 6PPD-Q toxicity in coho salmon, research has shifted to using zebrafish embryos and larvae when investigating the effects of environmental levels of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. The catalyst for the shift being a comparison between the similar life stages. Their short gestational times and transparent bodies make morphological studies simple and accessible. Evidence thus far has categorized zebrafish as a more "tolerant" species.(16) As new studies are published, the effects of PPDs seem to extend beyond mortality and into morphological, behavioral, and physiological changes."</p> <p>We also have a statement clarifying point (a) that we have moved to the introduction (lines 157-159) . This highlights that coho salmon focused on 6PPD-Q and zebrafish focused on 6PPD-Q and 6PPD.</p>
10	Same section: In general, I would avoid	We agree the one sentence summaries do not

	<p>providing one-line summaries of what was done in this or that study. They are not easy to read, and they do not directly communicate what you, as experts, are thinking. Instead, focus on the patterns and lessons in the research, and explain which recent study findings support your case. In this case, I think you are arguing something like: "We believe that the literature since the 2021 study indicates a need to better implement progressional life stages into toxicology studies. The field was caught off-guard not only by 6PPD-Q being the culprit exposure, but by insufficient attention to lifestage vulnerabilities of coho salmon. Systematic awareness of this issue will provide data that will help ensure that the data exists to support the goals of regulations intended to preserve the populations of species sensitive to 6PPD-Q and other analogous exposures. The following studies, we believe, support our case [then summarise the studies - a couple of sentences each about how they support your argument]. This will help with frontloading your arguments as well, and with tying your observations to your recommendations (see later comments).</p>	<p>flow well and are typically hard to write as these studies encompass many different discoveries. We have reviewed each of the studies and tried our best to group them/summarize them following the main trends of the researchers findings. This worked well without front loading - we specifically used your suggestion to introduce our goal or gap and follow it up with our evidence to support. In comment 8 we detail our methodology of how we tried to structure each section. For a specific example in section 4.2 Humans (lines 220-243) we introduce the gap as no regulation on daily intake, the current research diving into exposure, why we should be pursuing this avenue of research, followed by the current state of knowledge encompassing PPD exposure in humans.</p>
11	<p>Section "How does the mortality rate in zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>) compare to coho salmon?". As I understand it, the key issue here is that <i>danio rerio</i> is a species thought to be insensitive to 6PPD/Q, but may in fact not be. This suggests a section title such as "Insensitive species may be more sensitive than previously thought" may be better (rough suggestion, you can do better than me). This section also provides another example of how the argument is backloaded - if you lead out with your conclusion, then show how you get to it, it will be much easier for the reader to follow your argument. Your core claim here, I think, is that zebrafish may be more sensitive than previously thought (note "may", as this is opinion in a comment article), so just make that super-clear for the reader. They will thank you for it, because you are giving them a very clear steer on what you think is the trajectory of current research, which is what makes an expert commentary a useful type of</p>	<p>I switched around the introduction to expand more on the mortality seen between coho salmon and zebrafish and suggested that the label of "tolerant" may be more nuanced than we previously thought. Also see response to comment 9.</p> <p>Lines 165-173: "Since zebrafish LC50 values vary so greatly depending on methodology, the definitive categorization of zebrafish may be more nuanced than strictly "tolerant." We find, like the coho salmon studies, the experimental design, data acquisition, and analysis in zebrafish studies makes comparing LC50 values difficult. One study reported the estimated LC50 value for 6PPD to be 442.62 µg/L and 132.92 µg/L for 6PPD-Q after 96 hours of maintained exposure.(8) Alternatively, after 120 hours of stable exposure the measured LC50 value for 6PPD increased to 0.87 mg/L and no effect was</p>

	publication!	found in zebrafish embryos exposed to 6PPD-Q up to 10 mg/L.(18) This evidence further highlights the difficulty of comparing mortality rates between and within species.”
12	Section “How do PPDs affect zebrafish morphology, behavior, and physiology?” Is this a continuation of the potentially higher-than-expected sensitivity of insensitive species? If so, I suggest structuring accordingly - either by continuing the section rather than splitting it into sections, or introduce a subsection for each part of your argument.	Yes the morphology, behavior, and physiology sections may act as a continuation of the tolerance indicated by mortality. I rearranged the sections to further commentate on the nuance of zebrafish sensitivity. We did separate the sections into sub-sections that link back to our introduction paragraph for zebrafish. Sections 3.2-3.5, lines 156-192
13	Section “What is known about the metabolic fate of PPDs and their interactions with proteins” Here I could tentatively suggest a general section heading of "Mechanistic research into PPDs" or something like that. Then this would be a subsection and could be titled "PPD metabolites and their protein interactions" or something.	We changed this section title (section 5, line 282) to “Mechanistic research for PPDs” and added two subsections. 5.1 PPDs and Metabolic Fate (Line 283) 5.2 PPDs and Protein Interactions (Line 303)
14	Same section: The purpose of the section about metabolic fate is a bit less clear than the others and could benefit from being made more obvious to the reader. Is it that how PPDs are metabolised is not well known? Or that they have complex biological interactions that are associated with a range of important adverse outcomes, but the mechanistic picture is still unclear and needs to be further developed? How does this relate to the next section?	We have clarified why studying metabolic fate would be beneficial. As metabolism of the PPDs are expected to be biologically complex, transformation products may act as biomarkers to aid in the complete discovery of metabolic mechanisms. Lines 284-288 and Lines 304-307 reflect our topic sentences for each sub section and explain why metabolic fate and protein interactions are important for PPD toxicology research.
15	Section “How do PPDs affect gene regulation prior to the inflammatory response?” It looks like this section is about the immune response, within which you are focusing on inflammation. So it is probably a section "PPDs and gene regulation around the immune response" with subsections "Gene regulation prior to inflammatory response", "Gene regulation during" etc. It might be worth explaining to the reader why you focus on this aspect of the immune response - is it because	I clarified why we chose to investigate the inflammatory response sections as this is a particularly rich area within the PPD field right now. Lines 325-327: “This area of research is particularly rich, though recent publications indicate a need to map what is currently known across species in terms of the immune response (Figure 3).”

	<p>you have special expertise in this area, or because the literature here is particularly rich, or both, or other reason?</p>	
16	<p>Section "Conclusion": This is not strictly a conclusion, as more information is being added. I would suggest renaming it "Recommendations for research" or some such - it is not really "future trends" that you are describing, as much as future research that would make a difference for actionable evidence on PPDs? You can be explicit about that.</p>	<p>We renamed this section to Recommendations in PPD Research (line 383) and restructured our opening paragraph to lead into our recommendations (lines 392-394)</p> <p>We also removed Figure 4 although this was not a strict comment. We believe the writing speaks for itself. We also have quite a few other figures and tables that better represent our paper.</p>
17	<p>Same section: My main concern about the recommendations is they are rather generic and do not really respond to the previous discussion - there is a tendency to make a general point about a research method or knowledge goal, rather than ground the recommendation in what we do and don't know about PPDs. The reader should be informed about the direction they take their work in next. The fungal cell recommendation is the best, I think, and the other recommendations could be brought up to its level. Specific comments on the recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Transgenerational studies were barely mentioned in the commentary - do you raise it now as an apparent knowledge gap? ● Epigenetics: What is said here would be true of any substance, why specifically are you recommending this for PPDs? Your next recommendation is much more specific and substantive. Also, since this recommendation is more-or-less an extension of #1, maybe also think about combining them ● The discussion of fungal cell toxicology is an example where the future research is much more precisely described and motivated. This is the direction in which other recommendations could be developed. ● Cancer cell lines: This recommendation is also not specific to PPDs. ● Single-cell sequencing: This recommendation is also not specific to PPDs. 	<p>We agree that some of the recommendations are vague and not specific. We revised each section to encompass why we should use the suggested route to study PPDs.</p> <p>The transgenerational studies were briefly mentioned in section 4.2 line 223. We did our best to highlight this as a potential gap as we refined our front-loaded arguments. We also incorporated the epigenetics recommendation here. The suggestion to combine them made the most sense and we believe this recommendation is now up to the level of the fungal cell section.</p> <p>For cancer cell lines and single-cell sequencing we made these recommendations more specific by implementing a set structure to our recommendations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Why are we recommending this? (b) What gap or issue will this recommendation address? (c) How can this be implemented to fill the gap? <p>By implementing this formula into all of our recommendations we think this has solidified this section and made our recommendations stronger.</p> <p>Lastly, we addressed the progressional life stages in our introductory paragraph for our recommendations (line 389-391) while this is still an important field of study we suggest branching out into other avenues and deprioritizing but not halting progressional life stage studies.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I note that you do not, for example, mention research into progressional life stages, even though this seems quite fundamental to the initial part of your manuscript. Is there a reason for this? Are there other areas of research that you may have overlooked - in particular, any solved problems that can perhaps be deprioritised? 	<p>Mention your three bullet points you addressed in fungal and then how you mimicked in other points</p>
18	<p>Section (“aquatic organisms to what extent...”), page 5: The 2021 science study was already cited in the introduction yet reintroduced anew here, check to make sure the narrative flows cleanly across the sections.</p>	<p>We first introduced the 2021 study in the introduction (lines 69-70) so we completely reworked the lead into that particular study information. Lines 151-154: “One study reported juvenile lethal concentrations (LC50) as an average of $0.79 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g/L}$ after only 2 to 6 hours of exposure whereas another study found a constant 24 exposure decreased the median LC50 to 41.0 ng/L.(3,34)”</p> <p>Throughout our manuscript, we ensured stand out studies were only introduced once and then referenced accordingly later on in their specific sections.</p>
19	<p>Section on mice: This is another example of where the argument could be more front-loaded.</p>	<p>We rearranged the mouse section to be front-loaded. Specifically, we moved the major gap of no female mice models to the introduction before diving into what is currently published about male mice models. This is in section 4.1 lines 196-202: “Toxic effects of 6PPD-Q have also started to be studied in mammalian models such as male mice. Male mice offer a good fertility model because of their short reproductive times. Across many studies, 6PPD-Q has been found to complicate reproductive processes and induce inflammation responses.(35-41) However, there is still a major research gap including female mice models. Because of the wide effects of 6PPD-Q seen in other model organisms as well as male mice, additional studies focusing on female mice models would improve our understanding of the toxic mechanisms of PPDs.”</p>
20	<p>Sentence “It was noted that the mortality level was nowhere near complete sample mortality but was still significant when compared to the</p>	<p>We revisited the original author’s study and have omitted the referenced sentence as we agree this statement too strongly informs the reader of</p>

	control group” (p7). This reads like it might be a misunderstanding of statistical significance - presumably, the original authors reported a statistically significant 5% increase in mortality (or something like that)? In which case, the phrasing here is not ideal.	statistical significance.
21	Table 1. Please explain what “effect level” means and how it was determined. I am not convinced it is necessarily very meaningful, but could be persuaded otherwise.	I added a sentence to the table title clarifying “effect level” and added the reference that I forgot to add during the first round of peer review (lines 278-279).
22	Section “How do PPDs affect gene regulation of the inflammatory response?” This section feels a bit rushed compared to the others, some redrafting for clarity around the argument the authors are making would help the reader I think.	We reworked this section (section 6) to provide a more in depth background on cytokines and their subsequent pathways (lines 345-348). We then clarified which inflammation responses were attributed to specific PPD treatments (lines 349-361).